

Supplementary Table

CYB561 supports the neuroendocrine phenotype in castration-resistant prostate cancer

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S1 Table. Primers used to generate the pLKO.1-sh*CYB561* construct for lentiviral transduction.

h <i>CYB561-1</i> shRNA	Forward	CCGGGAGTCCTCCAGCCTGAATAACTCGAGTTATTCAGGCTGGAGGGACTCTTTTG
	Reverse	AATTCAAAAAGAGTCCTCCAGCCTGAATAACTCGAGTTATTCAGGCTGGAGGGACTC
h <i>CYB561-3</i> shRNA	Forward	CCGGGCACATCTTTGCGCTCGTCATCTCGAGATGACGAGCGCAAAGATGTGCTTTTG
	Reverse	AATTCAAAAAGCACATCTTTGCGCTCGTCATCTCGAGATGACGAGCGCAAAGATGTGC